

UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID
Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales

**High Power Bidirectional Wireless
Electric Vehicle Chargers: Advanced
Topology Solutions and Control
Strategies**

DOCTORAL THESIS

Submitted for the degree of Doctor by:

Nikola Mirković

Master's Degree in Electrical Engineering and Computer
Science at Belgrade University

Madrid, 2024

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